

Deliverable D5.2: The EUREKA Project website

EUREKA

European Knowledge Repository for best Agricultural Practices

Summary

Deliverable 5.2 is a description of the EUREKA project website. It was due in M3 (March 2020). Following a slight delay it was published online in M4 (late April 2020) at: www.h2020eureka.eu.

The reason for this delay was that a decision was taken during project inception to build the ‘brand platform’ of the EUREKA project on the existing visual identity of the closely-related EURAKNOS project, including the option of re-purposing of the EURAKNOS website for EUREKA. Whilst a sensible proposal, this option required some time for exploration, clarification and assessment of feasibility.

This report summarises development of the website.

Deliverable Number	Work Package
5.2	WP5
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Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date
M3 (March 2020)	M4 (April 2020)

Type of Deliverable			
R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)		
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos		X
E	Ethics		

Dissemination Level			
PU	Public		X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium		

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History of changes

Date	Changes
15 August 2022	Table 1 in Section 3 is updated to a) reflect the structure of the website at the end of the project and b) describe in more detail the related changes and developments. There are also some minor adjustments to the main text of the section.
	Comments regarding management of the website added have been added to Section 4.
	A new section 5 is added with final remarks and recommendations

Abbreviations Used

AU	Aarhus University (<i>project partner</i>)
C & D	Communication and dissemination
CMS	Content Management System
CSA	Co-ordination and support action
DoA	Description of Action
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability
HCC	Highclere Consulting (<i>project partner</i>)
LFG	Leap Forward Group (<i>project partner</i>)
M	Month of project implementation
MA	Multi-actor
PM	Person month
WP	Work package

1. Introduction

Deliverable 5.2 is a description of the EUREKA project website. It was due in M3 (March 2020), but delivered in M4 (late April).

During project development it was envisaged that the website would a) be the primary communication tool for the EUREKA project and b) be developed / managed in the frame of the project Communication Plan (Deliverable 5.3).

Deliverables 5.2 and 5.3 are the cornerstones of Task 5.2 (Development of the EUREKA Communication Plan and co-ordination of Communication Activities) of Work Package 5 (Develop an active MA community to promote and use the FarmBook).

In particular it was anticipated in the Description of Action (DoA) that the website would be compatible with:

“...the development of a unique, high quality visual identity / 'brand platform' style for the project, including logo design, colour palette, digital style guide, templates for newsletters, documents, presentations, social media content, project website. This will be supported by LFG and will be compatible with the branding of the database interface and platform of the FarmBook in T4.2.

The 'brand platform' will ensure a consistent, qualitative and correct development of EUREKA project website, as well as for the C & D of the project and the FarmBook platform; hence, the website design will be compatible with the database interface and FarmBook platform”.

2. Minor Deviation from the DoA

During the early stages of project inception (M1) it was decided by the Project Co-ordinators to adopt a slightly different approach to building the 'brand platform' for EUREKA by utilising – and further refining as necessary - the existing visual identity of the closely-related EURAKNOS project.

EURAKNOS was also co-ordinated by the University of Gent. It was a H2020 CSA that aimed to: 1) stimulate and intensify interactivity and knowledge exchange between the different H2020 Thematic Networks (plus linked EIP-AGRI Operational Groups and other H2020 multi-actor projects where relevant), and; 2) to search for a harmonised approach for setting up future thematic networks in order to maximise the impact upon practitioners, farmers and foresters.

During the EUREKA project kick-off meeting (27-30 January 2020) it was further agreed to also examine the feasibility of using the EURAKNOS website (www.euraknos.eu) as the basis of the EUREKA website (www.h2020eureka.eu).

This represents a minor deviation from the description of Task 5.2 in the DoA which anticipates the construction and maintenance of a **new website** by Aarhus University (AU). However, re-using and re-purposing the EURAKNOS website was clearly a logical course of action to explore and was encouraged by the Project Officer's recommendation that the EUREKA project works closely with the existing communication channels of the EURAKNOS project to avoid a) any unnecessary duplication of effort, and b) the risk of confusing users.

3. Agreed Approach

The EURAKNOS website was developed by Leap Forward (LFG) and they agreed to support both a) the re-purposing of the EURAKNOS website (including any additional development work needed) and b) the training of the AU team for using the associated Content Management System (CMS).

After a period of communication / clarification between AU and LFG, the AU team (with the support of other WP5 partners) reviewed the EURAKNOS website for the purposes of EUREKA and established that **re-purposing was feasible** in terms of:

- i) All technical aspects associated with re-using the existing EURAKNOS web structure and associated features / functionality as necessary;
- ii) The necessary adjustment / redrawing of graphics on the EURAKNOS website to suit the needs of EUREKA;
- iii) The PM resources allocated to LFG for WP5.

PLEASE NOTE - this assessment of feasibility assumed the ‘EU FarmBook’ Knowledge Reservoir would be developed and remain on a separate platform from the EUREKA project website. This is an important point and potential source of confusion. The main objective of the EUREKA project compared to EURAKNOS is the development of a **pilot version of the online ‘EU FarmBook’ platform** with the EUREKA project website performing a secondary supporting function as a communication and dissemination tool.

The final outcomes and conclusions from the process of re-purposing the EURAKNOS website are summarised in the Table below. The majority of the work involved in re-purposing was the ‘minimal adaptation’ of existing pages with the re-use of as many features and functions of the EURAKNOS website as possible.

Table 1

EURAKNOS webpages	EUREKA webpages	Adaptation & Comments
<p>Language Switch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> None 	<p>Language Switch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A dynamic Google Translate menu is visible on all pages at the EUREKA website. 14 languages are available (machine translation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Due to a limited budget for translation it was decided that LFG should implement a Google translation module to the website instead of manual translation which is a very time-consuming process.

EURAKNOS webpages	EUREKA webpages	Adaptation & Comments
<p>Footer on all pages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter subscription • Our partners • Get in touch 	<p>Footer on all pages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter subscription • Our partners • Get in touch 	<p>Minimal adaptation of EXISTING footer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AU worked in the dedicated development area to get familiar with the CMS dashboard • AU/LFG agreed and managed the necessary adaptation of these pages
<p>Home (https://euraknos.eu/)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intro text • Our mission • Map • Our thematic networks • What's going on (Events, Latest News and Tweets) • The EURAKNOS podcast 	<p>Home https://www.h2020eureka.eu/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • about EUREKA • news • practice abstracts • eu farmbook • deliverables • personas and user journeys 	<p>Minimal adaptation of EXISTING page</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AU worked in the dedicated development area to get familiar with the CMS dashboard • AU/LFG agreed and managed the necessary adaptation of these pages • AU has been responsible for all ongoing content management
<p>About (https://euraknos.eu/about)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What we do? • How we do it? 	<p>About (https://h2020eureka.eu/about)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What we did • How we did it • Main objectives • project structure 	<p>Minimal adaptation of EXISTING page</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As above
<p>Thematic Networks (https://euraknos.eu/thematic-network)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links to Thematic Networks 		
<p>News (https://euraknos.eu/news)</p> <p>Links to new stories</p>	<p>News (https://h2020eureka.eu/news)</p> <p>Links to new stories</p>	<p>Minimal adaptation of EXISTING page</p> <p>As above</p>
	<p>Practice Abstracts (https://h2020eureka.eu/practice-abstracts)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links to uploaded Practice Abstracts (50) (downloadable PDF versions of the EIP-AGRI common format) 	<p>NEW PAGE - the design of the practice abstract page was changed by the end of the project to make room for 50 PA's and to give a better overview of them.</p>
	<p>EU Farmbook https://h2020eureka.eu/eufarmbook</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All relevant material and 	<p>NEW PAGE – based on copying and adapting EXISTING page – this page was developed by the</p>

EURAKNOS webpages	EUREKA webpages	Adaptation & Comments
	information related to the EU FarmBook (videos, manuals etc.)	end of the project and replaced the “press area” that contained press kit, PowerPoint templates, logo’s etc.
Deliverables https://euraknos.eu/deliverables Downloads	Deliverables https://h2020eureka.eu/deliverables <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Links to uploaded public deliverables (downloadable PDF versions) 	Minimal adaptation of EXISTING page
	Personas and user journeys https://h2020eureka.eu/personas-and-user-journeys <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fictional representations of specific groups of end-users which have been created to design and structure EU FarmBook. 	NEW PAGE The personas and user journeys were originally placed at the ‘home’ page. They were moved to a more logic and prominent position - to highlight their importance to the project and to make it easier to find them.

4. Site Management

The AU team have responsibility for content management with one-to-one technical support provided by LFG. All supporting documentation has been prepared and provided.

LFG initially gave the AU team access to a dedicated web development area to familiarise themselves with the CMS.

AU as web editor on the EUREKA website, has experienced limitations in connection with the website system built by LFG. The limitations lie in the way the design is constructed. It does not allow the web editor to make quite simple changes on the individual pages. As an example of this, it has not been possible to implement graphs/models/images in news stories related to the text. It has only been possible to insert *one* image per news item, which is "blown up" in a very large format in the header. Some news stories requires more images (minor images), graphs or models – but the design made this impossible.

In addition, it has been extremely challenging that the web editor has been ‘locked in’ by the design that was agreed upon at the beginning of the project. Websites are dynamic and changes occur continuously. During the process, it has not been possible for the web editor herself to make small changes on the individual pages of a structural nature or changes related to content (possibility of links to Youtube, PDF, images etc.). Thus, the web editor had to involve LFG every time a minor or major change had to take place. This process has been time-consuming and inflexible.

5. Final remarks and recommendations

A comprehensive description of the EU FarmBook and its benefits is provided on the EUREKA website (home/about): <https://h2020eureka.eu/about>

The EU FarmBook is also linked to the project website together with guidance on its use: <https://h2020eureka.eu/eufarmbook>. Links to supporting materials (e.g. videos and manuals) are also provided on this page. All text on the EUREKA website has been reviewed to ensure it is up-to-date.

Overall the EUREKA website is a well-structured platform with a simple and modern design. However, there continues to be scope for improvements, notably:

- More flexibility in the CMS-system to make changes (for the web-editor)
- ‘Subpages’ would make room for a better and more logical structure

That said, given the limitations of the CMS **it is not recommended for the website to be taken over** by any subsequent projects. A new website should be constructed.